

SCOPE OF RESEARCH IN KAYACHIKITSA- A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: Kayachikitsa, the branch of Ayurveda focused on internal medicine, plays a crucial role in prevention and management of chronic diseases through holistic approaches. With growing global interest in integrative medicine, there is a need for scientific validation of Ayurvedic principles and therapies. **Objective:** This article explores the scope of research in Kayachikitsa, identifying key areas such as clinical validation, pharmacological studies, personalized medicine, mental health interventions, and integrative healthcare. The objective is to highlight research ideas that bridge traditional Ayurvedic knowledge with modern scientific methodologies. **Methods:** A comprehensive review of existing literature, clinical studies, and pharmacological research on Ayurvedic interventions was conducted. Additionally, emerging trend in genomics, artificial intelligence, and herbal drug standardization were analyzed to assess their applicability in

Ayurveda-based healthcare models. **Results:** Findings suggest that Ayurveda has significant potential in managing metabolic disorders, neurological conditions, and autoimmune diseases. Phytochemical studies reveal bioactive compounds with anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties, supporting the need for further drug development. Personalized medicine in Ayurveda, particularly through Prakriti-based classifications, aligns with advancements in precision medicine. Integrative healthcare models incorporating Ayurveda with modern medicine demonstrate promising outcomes in chronic disease management.

Conclusion: Research in Kayachikitsa holds immense potential for evidence-based integration into mainstream healthcare. However, challenges such as standardization, clinical validation, and regulatory frameworks must be addressed. Future studies should focus on large-scale clinical trials, interdisciplinary collaborations, and the development of standardized treatment protocols to establish Ayurveda as a globally recognized system of medicine.

KEYWORDS: Kayachikitsa, Ayurveda, integrative medicine, clinical validation, phytochemistry, personalized medicine, holistic healthcare.

INTRODUCTION

The word “Research” is derived from French word ‘recherche’ which means ‘to go about seeking’.^[1] ‘Re’ (prefix)- new or over again or continuous and ‘search’ (verb)- to examine or to look or to probe. Research is defined as “systematic, careful study and investigation in any field of knowledge, undertaken to establish facts or principles”.^[2] Other terms that are used for research include Discovery, invention, exploration, inquiry, revalidation, revelation, reorientation, verification, etc. To a doctor, research may mean the evaluation of effectiveness of a particular treatment, To a bio-medical professional, research may mean the development of new techniques and equipment etc. for better treatment, To people in business and industry, research may mean solving various operational and planning problems. To social scientists, research may mean the study of social relationships and obtaining answers to various social problems. To the government, research may mean collecting information on the economic and social structure of the nation which acts as a tool in devising various government policies. Hence, research is the fountain of knowledge and an important source of providing guidelines for solving various economic, governmental, and social problems.

The term 'Research' is not new for Ayurveda. Centuries ago, Ayurveda stressed on the constant need for research in every aspect of the medical science.

Anveshana (अन्वेषण) –

इष्यतेऽन्विष्यते साध्यतेऽनयेत्येषणाः ।

Continuous desire to search is called as Anveshana.

कार्यकारणभावस्य द्रव्याणां गुणकर्मयोः ।

परीक्ष्य स्थापनं सम्यक् अनुसंधानम् उच्यते ॥(Priyavat Sharma)

The study of cause and effect relationship between dravya, guna and karma after several observations and through verifiable examinations, arriving at final conclusion is known as Anusandhan.

Eshana (एषण), Gaveshana (गवेषण), Paryeshana (पर्येषण), Manthana (मंथन), Pareekshya (परीक्ष्य), Pratipatti (प्रतिपत्ति) are some of other terminology used for Research in Ayurveda.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Different types of research have been explained according to different fields of application. According to CCRAS research is classified into 6 section as follows:-

1. Literary research and documentation
2. Drug standardization research
3. Medicinal plant research (Medico-ethno Botanical survey, cultivation, Pharmacognosy)
4. Pharmacology research (Pre clinical safety/toxicity and biological activity studies)
5. Fundamental research
6. Clinical research

Kayachikitsa, is the 1st branch of ashtanga ayurveda as stated by Acharya Charaka and Vagbhata, it is defined as

कायचिकित्सा नाम सर्वाङ्गसंश्रितानां व्याधीनां ज्वररक्तपित्तशोषोन्मादा- पस्मार कुष्ठमेहातिसारादीनामुपशमनार्थम् । (सु. सूत्र 1/8)

It deals with concepts of *Dosha-dathu-mala vikalpa vigyana, Agni, Ama, Avarana, Roga-rogi pariksha, Rasayana-Vajikarana, Trividha chikitsa, Anupana, Aushadasevana kala, Pathya-Apathya*. Etc.

And hence from the definition it's clearly denotes that, Kayachikitsa the branch of Ayurveda, which mainly involved in clinical research.

Clinical research is a branch of health care science that determines the safety and effectiveness of medication, devices, diagnostic products and treatment regimens intended for human use.^[3]

Types of clinical research

Based on researchers behave:- Observational, Interventional.

Based on the purpose:- Prevention trials, Screening trials, Diagnostic trials, Treatment trials, Quality of life, Compassionate use trials.

PRE REQUIREMENTS OF CLINICAL TRIAL

Intervention Details

Drug:- (in vitro & in vivo studies)

Quality assurance & standardization of the trial drugs.

Safety/toxicity studies & Biological activity.

Therapy/ Procedure:- SOP for

Panchakarma procedures.

Parasurgical procedures.

Data on pilot/preliminary study(if needed)

Scope & Importance of research in Kayachikitsa

For the easy understanding, we can classify Clinical research in Ayurveda under the heading of:-

हेतुलिङ्गौषधज्ञानं स्वस्थातुरपरायणम् ।

त्रिसूत्रं शाश्वतं पुण्यं बुबुधे यं पितामहः ॥(Ch.Su.1/24)

1. Hetu
2. Linga
3. Aushadha

Scope of research related to “Hetu/nidana” i.e, to explore the cause, where Pariksha is very important.

Development of Diagnostic tools like Software and Questionnaires for Pariksha

Currently there are many researches which have been undertaken in these section like, Correlation of prakriti diagnosis using AyuSoft prakriti diagnostic tool with clinical rating in patients with psychiatric disorders.^[4]

SUMMARY

Prakriti assessment by AyuSoft software in stabilised psychiatric patient, was correlated with Prakriti assessed by two Ayurvedic physician.

The study showed high reliability with Ayusoft prakriti diagnosis.

Standardizing techniques for assessing prognosis of a disease

Assessment of prognosis aspects of cancer by Taila bindhu pariksha.^[5]

SUMMARY

A pilot study, on a single group of 20 subjects who were advised radio and chemotherapy.

The results obtained from taila bindu pariksha, were compared with ECOG(Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group)- scale and the results showed statistically highly significant correlation. And concludes as Taila Bindu Pariksha may be used as an alternative method to assess the prognosis of the Cancer patients.

Standardizing classically explained Diagnostic methods

Examination and diagnosis of Rasavaha srotas disorders in Ayurveda: Methods and approach.^[6]

SUMMARY

The article given knowledge on Rasavaha sroto vikara and the general examination to be carried out during the condition with laboratory investigation.

By integrating traditional diagnostic methods with modern approaches, practitioners can gain comprehensive insights into the underlying causes of imbalance and frame personalized treatment, to restore health and well-being.

So, in further there is need of standardizing each parikshas mentioned in classics with specific to srotas & their diseases, to explore Hetu.

Scope of research related to “Linga/Rupa” i.e, to understand the signs & symptoms, by framing Samprapti of a condition.

Describing Pathogenesis of new diseases

Pathophysiology of COVID-19 and host centric approaches in Ayurveda.^[7]

SUMMARY

The article gives details as the pathogenesis of any new diseases can be understood with the help of existing knowledge of Srotas, roga marga, nidana panchaka. etc and the condition can be assessed using different parameters like agni, bala, symptom graded scale. Etc.

Nomenclature of new diseases

After validating the Pathogenesis of new diseases, even though our acharyas have mentioned “there is no important to name the disease and to treat based on symptoms” (Ch\Su18\ 44), Naming the disease becomes much needed in modern era.

For ex:- Even though there are numerous diseases coming under Cardiovascular system, in Ayurveda the entire concept are included under single heading.

It is important to note WHO in collaboration with Minst. of Ayush, to include data and terminology related to diseases based on ASU system in TM2 module of ICD-11 classification.

This will lead to global uniformity in ASU medicine as a code of vocabulary defining diseases.

Scope of research related to “Aushada” i.e, standardising treatment and development of EBM.

The main aim here is to develop Evidence based medicine. Under trials can be focused on different and varying application of treatment like,

1. Trial on different type of chikitsa mentioned.
2. Trial on different approach to diseases.
3. Validating chikitsa sutra.
4. Single drug trial.
5. Drug development.
6. Study on efficacy of different form of same medication.
7. Collaborative studies.
8. Athyayika chikitsa.
9. Treatment in Jara and vrusha.
10. Other untouched areas like developing treatment instruments, Anupana and so on...

1. Clinical study on Trivida chikitsa:- *Yuktivyapashraya, Satvavajaya and Daivavyapashraya chikitsa.*

Yuktivyapashraya:- Studies can be framed based on the yukti of vaidya like,

To evaluate the efficacy of Nityavirechana and Trayodashanga Guggulu in the management of Katigraha(low backache) in Overweight and Obesity.^[8]

Result:- study shows highly significant with $p < 0.001$, in the parameters assessed using VAS scale, body weight and BMI in a pre and post study design.

Satvavajaya:- Research work can be framed based on Satvavajaya principle like,

A clinical study on role of Shankapushpi Syrup and Satvavajaya chikitsa in management of Shyamamutrata(Nocturnal Enuresis) in pediatric practice.^[9]

Result:- The group which received Satvavajaya chikitsa and Shankapushpi Syrup better result than the group receiving Shankapushpi syrup only.

Daivavyapashraya:- It is most untouched aspect of principal under research in Ayurveda, studies can be framed based on the different treatment which can be adopted under daivavyapashraya like,

Yagnya therapy as supportive care in cancer patients improved QOL: 3 Case studies.^[10]

Result:- Average % improvement in all three individual condition, on 10-scale questionnaire, including physical and psychological complaints were 75%, 41.67% and 40%, respectively.

2. Validating chikitsa sutra

Longitudinal studies can be framed based on application of chikitsa sutra to individual disease like,

An open longitudinal clinical trial to validate chikitsa sutra of amavata vis-a-vis Rheumatoid arthritis.^[11]

Result:- Study was carried out assessing the efficacy of chronological administration of treatment principles described in Chakradatta, i.e. Langhana, Swedana, Tikta deepana katu dravya sevana, Virechana, Snehapana and Basti. In this study Snehapana is administered after Basti in the form of Shamana sneha.

The study was a single group open clinical trial with pre and post test design with the sample size of 40 subjects. The study concludes as “Chikitsa sutra of Amavata is effective in management with P value 0.000”

3. Single drug study

Ayurveda has explained innumerable Ekamoolika drugs for many diseases. So study can be framed based on these drugs.

Role of Kapikachu white seeds in the management of Klaibya: A clinical study.^[12]

Summary: The trial drug in the dose of 5 gm twice daily with anupana of luke warm milk was administered to all the patients for 1 month. Result of study shown that there is highly significant result in sexual desire, total sperm count and rapid linear progressive (RLP) motility of sperms. So it can be concluded that Kapikacchu white seeds churna is effective in the management of Klaibya.

4. Development of different forms of medication and testing their effectiveness

These studies are mainly intended to improve the palatability of medication by changing their form of use, without compromising in their effectiveness.^[13]

Conclusion:- These studies can only be taken as a preliminary step towards the betterment of traditional medicine. These drugs are to be further individually analysed to assess the major active compounds and its efficacy.

5. COLLABORATIVE OR INTEGRATIVE RESEARCH

Collaborative research research involving different system of science working together to achieve common goal of developing new knowledge.

It is the prime need for present day Ayurveda, to go, hand in hand with other system of medicine and other field of science. Which can serve as stepping stone for integration.

Collaboration may start within the departments of same system of medicine, different system of medicine, food and nutrition, IT sector or any field of science.

Table No. 1: Table showing some of collaborative studies.

Institutes	Collaborating Institution	Research area
CCRAS	AMUL, Gujarat	To develop Nutritional supplement for school going children, Pregnant women geriatric population.
Central research institute, Mumbai	TATA Cancer research institute	1. Improvement of QOL in Cancer patient. 2. Screening of Herbal drugs for potential anti-Cancer activity.
CCRAS	Govt. Ayurveda college and Hospital, Nanded	Yavakshara ointment in piles(in progress)
CCRAS	AIIMS, New delhi	AyushRasayana in Geriatric population.

6. THERAPEUTIC STRATEGY:- RASAYANA CHIKITSA

There is wide scope in development of Drug-oriented therapy study and developing the SOP, aiming in immune development, Curative aspect, QOL, Preventive aspect or Preventing Recurrence of a condition.

Clinical evaluation of Vardhamana Pippali Rasayana in the management of Amavata (Rheumatoid Arthritis)^[14]

Summary:- observations and discussion of this study, the following conclusions was drawn. Vardhamana Pippali Rasayana was effective in the management of Amavata and It is also very much cost-effective.

7. GERIATRIC

A clinical study of Punarnava Mandura in the management of Pandu roga in old age(geriatric anemia)^[15]

Summary: Single arm study with 100 subjects, who were given Punarnava mandoora in 1BD dose with anupana as Takra.

Result:- There was beneficial effect in patients of Pandu roga, by providing highly significant result in Kshaya of Dhatu, Agni bala, Deha bala and Satwa bala. It has also improved QOL of the patients, Moderate and mild improvement was seen in 30% and 70% of the patient respectively.

8. EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT IN AYURVEDA

Even though ayurveda has very minimal role in emergency condition, when compared to latest development in modern science, there are some references in ayurvedic classics which are practiced by folklore practitioners.

9. Validating SOP for procedures

SOP can be validated by conducting large sample clinical trials in multicenter format with prior strict Literary review, to assess the efficacy and feasibility. This will reduce the incidence of complication in any procedure undertaken and also serve as a research guideline.

SOP FOR UTTARBASTI I.E. UTERINE DETOX THERAPY OF AYURVEDA
W.S.R. TO INFERTILITY WITH IMPLANTATION DEFECTS^[16]

The study concludes stating that, these studies should be carried out in large sample, so this will help in standardising the treatment procedure.

10. Development of new instruments and materials for treatment

Which are Easy to handle, Portable, Increasing their availability, Easy to use, Machine monitored, Cost effective and Reduces man power requirement.

11. Anupana

In classics we have mentioning of different Anupana, with specific to diseases and drugs, which are not explored. This shows the richness of traditional science, where in modern we don't have any reference on change in action of a drug with respect to anupana.

12. Therapeutic utility of Herbal formulation

Unlike western medicine, involving single chemical and probable single target and action. Our drugs are very different with multiple ingredients, multiple active principles and multiple targets. So, these mode of action of formulation can be understood with modern science under the principle of Network pharmacology. And further we can include in the digital database like Pubchem etc.

So, there is need for studying each formulation, finding the mode of action to answer the questions of modern world. This is possible only by studying and applying modern technology in our science.

13. Drug development

What has been done.?

Starting from the setting up of Central Institute of Research in Indigenous Systems of Medicine (CIRISM), in the year 1953, One of the most productive contributions from this institute was the research on Panduroga, using Punarnavamandoora and Navayasachoorna.

Now there has been milestone in development of new drugs for different diseases like, Ayush-64 for Malaria, 777 oil for Psoriasis, Ayush-56 for Epilepsy etc.

What is going on.?

Validation and development of formulations for disease/clinical conditions Like Epilepsy, Filariasis, Cardiovascular disease, Hemiplegia, Malaria, Obesity, Lipid disorder, Paraplegia, Peptic Ulcer, Mental Retardation, Bronchial Asthma, Chronic Bronchitis, Cognitive Deficit, Dyslipidemia, Essential Hypertension, Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS), Iron Deficiency Anemia. etc.

AYUSH FUNDING for EXTRA MURAL RESEARCH in Ayurveda, where the first aim includes the development of R&D based Ayurveda Drugs for prioritised diseases.

DISCUSSION

Some of the topics like Avarana or diseases like Kampavata which are either shortly described and less clarified or which may raise doubts, are to be standardised with the help of various exposition techniques like tantra yukti, Vada marga.

Even after development of SOP of some disorders like Amavata, Tamaka shwasa, there are relatively many leftover diseases, which are to be addressed and SOP are to be developed like Kshudra rogas.

The question related to need of RCT in ayurvedic clinical trial remains questionable, as the number variable factors like Prakriti, Agni that affect the treatment principle are more. Some clinical concepts like Aushada sevana kala, Visha chikitsa, Naimitika rasayana need explorative studies.

Life style disorders are increasing day by day, so observational studies related to Nidana, are to be framed, which will definitely serve as Preventive care for life style disorders.

Identifying the role of Ayurveda in preventive and curative concept, and framing of Collaborative research, with other stream of medicine and science is much required in present era. Knowledge of Biochemical action and understanding mode of action of herbal formulation is required, so there is need for generating data and quantifying it.

Herbal formulations, in which many are indicated in multiple systemic diseases are to be studied in an explorative approach with concern to Herb-drug interaction, target areas etc. There is need for bringing harmony among the different streams of medicine, to promote integrative approach, aiming at providing better health for mankind.

There are many animal studies conducted and left untouched for human trial, so there can be initiative to identify and carryout trial. It is quite evident Kayachikitsa needs research which are longitudinal, multicenter, interdisciplinary clinical trials in developing Evidence based medicine.

CONCLUSION

The process of research is continuous and nothing can be left out without subjecting to process of proving. Any stream of science including Ayurveda are to be revised and validated to answer questions of modern world.

Kayachikitsa the prime branch of Ayurveda which is mainly involved in clinical research, aims in developing Evidence base medicine and gain Global acceptance and flourish Ayurveda as a global science.

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